

Appendix 1. Laboratory test

This section shows the tests evaluated to the students, at the beginning and at the end of the experimental activities of the mechanical standing waves laboratory.

The tests: previous concepts test and update concepts test, contain the same questions.

Student name:.....

Q1. When a wave propagates it is because energy is propagated and for this reason the particles in the medium where they propagate move. Does a node contradict this phenomenon?

Q2. Does the superposition of mechanical waves that travel in the same medium necessarily have the same frequency, wavelength and speed?

Q3. Are resonant frequencies always multiples of the fundamental frequency?

Q4. On what variables does the resonant frequency of mechanical waves that interfere to form standing waves in elastic media such as strings or springs depend?

Appendix 2. Laboratory Guide for Students

Experiment 1: Transversal Stationary Waves

1. Materials

- PocketLab-Voyager sensor (Myriad Sensors, Inc.)
- Plastic strap or tape to hold the PocketLab sensor to the wrist
- A plastic spring
- A measuring tape
- An electronic mobile device such a cellphone, tablet, or laptop with Bluetooth connector, and a functional PocketLab application.

2. Instructions

2.1. Fix the sensor to your wrist and turn it as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The PocketLab Voyager sensor is attached to the wrist with the help of a strap.

2.2. Open the PocketLab application on your Bluetooth enabled device and link it to the sensor. Select to register Acceleration Scalar and choose a sampling frequency of 50 Hz.

Figure 2. (a) PocketLab-voyager sensor selection, (b) selection to register scalar acceleration, (c) set the sampling frequency to 50 Hz. Figures of the PocketLab app on iOS.

- 2.3. Using a measuring tape, elongate the spring for two to three meters where one end will be held by the person with the sensor on the wrist.
- 2.4. The person holding the sensor will move up and down the spring to generate an stationary wave on its first harmonic as shown on Figure 3.

Figure 3. Formation of standing waves in a spring for the first, second and third harmonics.

2.5. When the first harmonic is established, start recording data (Figure 4a) for at least 10 seconds with the PocketLab application.

Figure 4. (a) Figure where the record button (red circle) is displayed. (b) Figure after pressing stop recording data. (c) Figure that shows how to select to send data by e-mail.

2.6. After recording data, send them to an e-mail or any other type of cloud storage available by clicking on the sharing icon highlighted on Figure 4b and select the type of data to share (Figure 4c).

2.7. Repeat procedures 2.4 to 2.6 to generate the data when establishing second, third and fourth harmonic. (Figure 3).

2.8. Repeat procedures 2.4 to 2.6 to generate data for first or second harmonic while holding the tension at distances of 3, 4, 5 and 6 meters.

2.9. Repeat instructions 2.4 to 2.6 to generate data for first or second harmonic while holding the tension at a fixed distance between 3 to 6 meters while varying the tension on the spring for at least five different values. For most commercial plastic springs, we recommend using a T_0 with a distance of 1,065 m because the distance of the spring without tension is 6,5 cm; and then the suggested tension values might be $2T_0$, $3T_0$, $4T_0$, $5T_0$, $6T_0$.

Experiment 2: Stationary sound waves in a semi-open tube

1. Materials

- A smart phone with a frequency generator functional application
- A measuring tape
- PVC plastic tube 6 inches in diameter and 1,8 m in length
- An Styrofoam or silicone disk 6 inches in diameter and 10 cm in length
- A 1,5 long wooden stick
- Sticky tack paddy

2. Instructions

- 2.1. Fix horizontally the PVC tube with the sticky tack to a long table or flat surface. Cover one end with the Styrofoam disk and place the smartphone to the other end while emitting a sound at a frequency of $f = 250$ Hz using an application for frequency generation (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Scheme of the experiment to generate standing waves in a semi-open tube.

- 2.2. Move the disk inside the tube with the help of the wooden stick (Figure 6) until perceiving a strong intense sound corresponding to the formation of a stationary wave.
- 2.3. Find the position where the sound intensity is the highest and measure the distance L with the measuring tape as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Scheme showing the styrofoam disk displaced inside the PVC tube until standing waves are generated at an effective length equal to L .

- 2.4. Displace the disk towards the smartphone until finding the following harmonics until the frequency of 250 Hz.
- 2.5. Repeat 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4 for other four starting frequencies.
- 2.6. Build a table with the effective length, the harmonic number and the frequency for each measurement performed.

Appendix 3. Survey about the laboratory learning methodology

Name and surname:.....

The purpose of this survey is to collect your views on the physics laboratory pilot. You will be able to score between very good and bad, depending on your experience.

	Very Good	Good	Avarage	Bad
The experiences of laboratory 1 and 2 have been				
The plenary discussion of the groups has been				
The development of the laboratory 3				
The laboratory guide has been				
The idea of using Smartphones has been				
The idea of using the pocket laboratory				
In general, the laboratory has seemed				

A. Give your opinion on the development of Physics Laboratory: (comment)

B. Express with a sentence what you would comment to a partner who is going to participate in this laboratory

C. Rate the laboratory experience with a score of 0 to 20 points:

D. Give your opinion about your participation in the Physics laboratory:

	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Regular	Bad
My motivation has been					
My participation has been					
The advantage of the sessions has been					
My time to experiment has been					
It has allowed me to complete the theory in a way					

E. Point out 3 positive aspects and 3 negative aspects of the development of the Physics laboratory:

Positive aspects	Negative aspects
1	1
2	2
3	3

F. Mark with an X what you consider fits the scale, where:

(5) Strongly Agree (4) Somewhat Agree (3) Neither Agree/Neither Disagree (2) Somewhat Disagree (1) Strongly Disagree

	5	4	3	2	1
The laboratory guide is precisely and clearly formulated					
The materials used in the laboratory were adequate					
The time allotted for each activity was correct					
The head of practice is required to be present in the laboratory					
The laboratory allowed applying the theory learned in the course					
You learned or reinforced new knowledge of Physics					
All the members of the group participated in the experiences.					
The instructions provided for the laboratory were necessary					
There was internal discussion in the group to answer the question guide					
You have been able to contribute your creativity to the development of the experiences					
In the development of the laboratory it was possible to work as a team					
The laboratory helped to relate physics with reality					

G. List what you learned in these 3 sessions of the Physics 2 laboratory:

Session: Tuesday 9	Session: Wednesday 10	Session: Thursday 11
1	1	1
2	2	2
3	3	3

H. Write your general comment regarding the development of the 3 sessions of the Physics laboratory